

Co-Creating Science in Rural Communities

Practical insights from organising a Rural European Researchers' Night in Armamar, Portugal

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15390687>

Raquel Branquinho^{1,2}; **Cândida Sarabando^{1,3}**; **Joaquim Duarte^{1,3}**; **Cláudia Damião^{1,4}**; **Sara Carrulo^{1,2}**; **Ana Santos Carvalho^{5,6,7,8}**; **Daniela Ribeiro^{9,10,11}**; **Inês Duarte^{1,12}**; **Joana B. Barbosa¹³**; **Joana C. Barbosa¹³**; **Márcio Carochó^{14,15,16}**; **Mariana Fernandes¹⁷**; **Marlene Lúcio^{1,18}**; **Raul Bartolomeu^{14,19,20,21}**; **Richard Marques¹⁰**; **Sofia Friães^{1,22}**; **Susana Ambrósio^{12,23}**; **Xana Sá-Pinto¹²**

1 ARMA-Sci - Network for the Promotion of Armamar's Science Capital (*Rede de Promoção do Capital Científico de Armamar*), Armamar, Portugal 2 University of Porto - Faculty of Arts and Humanities, Porto, Portugal 3 Gomes Teixeira School Cluster (AEGT), Armamar, Portugal 4 Armamar's Municipality, Culture and Science Council, Armamar, Portugal 5 Gene Therapy Center of Excellence (GeneT), Coimbra, Portugal 6 Center for Innovation in Biomedicine and Biotechnology (CIBB), Coimbra, Portugal 7 University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal 8 SciComPT Network, Portugal 9 University of Porto - Faculty of Sciences, Porto, Portugal 10 Institute of Education and Citizenship (IEC), Mamarrosa, Portugal 11 Association for World Innovation in Science and Health Education (AWISHE), Mamarrosa, Portugal 12 University of Aveiro - Department of Education and Psychology - Research Centre on Didactics and Technology in the Education of Trainers (CIDTFF), Aveiro, Portugal 13 Universidade Católica Portuguesa (UCP) -Faculty of Biotechnology (ESB), Centre of Biotechnology and Fine Chemistry (CBQF), Porto, Portugal 14 Polytechnic Institute of Bragança (IPB), Bragança, Portugal 15 Mountain Research Centre (CIMO), Bragança, Portugal 16 Associate Laboratory for Sustainability and Technology in Mountains Regions (SusTEC), Bragança, Portugal 17 Universidade de Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro, Centro de Química de Vila Real (CQ-VR), Vila Real, Portugal 18 Centro de Física das Universidades do Minho e Porto (CF-UM-UP)/LaPMET (Laboratório de Física para Materiais e Tecnologias Emergentes)/CBMA-Centro de Biologia Molecular e Ambiental da Universidade of Minho, Braga, Portugal 19 Polytechnic Institute of Guarda (IPG), Bragança, Portugal 20 Sport Physical Activity and Health Research & Innovation Center (SPRINT), Rio Maior, Portugal 21 Research Center for Active Living and Wellbeing (LiveWell), Bragança, Portugal 22 Instituto de Investigación Química Andrés M. del Río (IQAR)/Departamento de Química Orgánica y Química Inorgánica, Universidad de Alcalá, Spain 23 Yellow Lemon - Scientific Consulting and Training

✉ redesciencia.armamar@gmail.com

1. Context & Rationale

Why this matters?

Most European Researchers' Night (ERN) events are concentrated in urban, academic settings — universities, science museums, or research hubs. This urban bias creates a geographic and social asymmetry in access to science, systematically excluding rural and underserved communities. Portugal is no exception. ERN events remain clustered in cities, leaving remote territories with little or no opportunity for scientific engagement.

What we did?

In Armamar, a remote village in northern Portugal, we piloted a new approach: Rural European Researchers' Night (RERN), in 2023 [1,3] and 2024 [2], co-created with students, teachers, researchers, and local institutions.

Our aim was to create an event that would bring science to rural areas, but also empower local actors to lead it — shaping a replicable, community-owned model for inclusive science engagement.

2. How we did it?

8 building blocks for rural science engagement

1. Local co-ownership

The event was co-designed with local schools, the municipality, NGOs, university partners, and local students, ensuring shared responsibility and relevance from the outset.

2. Students as co-organisers

Secondary school students took active roles in planning, logistics, evaluation, and communication. Their participation was formally recognised and embedded in their school records.

3. Local ambassadors network

A strategic network of local researchers, teachers, students, and alumni mobilised both academic and local community networks, building trust and increasing reach.

4. "Adopt a Scientist" program

Based on their interest areas, students were paired with researchers, supporting activities and fostering dialogue. This approach helped overcome potential initial communication barriers, created lasting mentor relationships and enhanced students' science identity.

5. Place-based, hands-on activities, designed for dialogue

Science formats that promote meaningful engagement (e.g. science stations, flash talks, fish bowl, Q&A sessions, collaborative tours) address locally relevant themes — including agriculture, health, sustainability, AI, environmental pollution, sociology, education, among others.

6. Researcher support & incentives

Researchers received specialized training (e.g. science communication, research impact), comprehensive logistical support, and cultural experiences.

7. Informal & inclusive venues

The event was held in familiar and accessible community spaces - from the village museum to the local sports pavilion - central, accessible, and familiar, reinforcing a sense of belonging and lowering participation barriers for first-time attendees. Using familiar locations helped overcome residents' intimidation toward formal scientific settings.

8. Plan for continuity

The event was planned as a catalyst for long-term science engagement - fostering sustainable initiatives such as school-based programs, community-led associations, and ongoing researcher-community collaborations.

3. Reflections & What's Next

RERN-Armamar sparked several outcomes:

- **Participants' enhanced scientific literacy:** participants perceived enhanced content knowledge and science identity.
- **ARMA-Sci (*Rede de Promoção do Capital Científico de Armamar*):** a local science NGO now active year-round.
- **Community publication:** A co-authored book with 62 community voices [3].
- **Academic advancement:** A PhD scholarship on science education.
- **Sustainable growth:** An expanding event with increasing participation.

RERN-Armamar highlights the potential of rural communities to co-design and sustain meaningful science engagement initiatives. It also offers a replicable model for inclusive, place-based science engagement, rooted in trust, co-creation, and local relevance.

Could your next science outreach project start in a village like Armamar?

References

- [1] Branquinho, R., Sá-Pinto, X, Ambrósio, S. (2023) Promoting science for all: how European Researchers' Night could unlock science in rural Portugal. PLOS SciComm. <https://scicomm.plos.org/2023/11/07/promoting-science-for-all-how-european-researchers-night-could-unlock-science-in-rural-portugal/>
- [2] Branquinho, R., Duarte, I., Friães, S., Ambrósio, S., Sá-Pinto, X,(2024) Empowering through Science: How Armamar is Building Bridges to Science in Rural Communities. PLOS SciComm. <https://scicomm.plos.org/2024/11/08/empowering-through-science-how-armamar-is-building-bridges-to-science-in-rural-communities/>.
- [3] Branquinho, R., et al. (2024). Noite Europeia dos Investigadores em Armamar – Palco da Ciência em Ambientes Rurais. UA Editora. <https://doi.org/10.48528/vh3d-zx88>.
- [4] Branquinho, R., et al. (2025). Seedling Science Communication in Rural Areas through European Researchers' Night. JCOM. Accepted. *in press*.